

Physical Damage and Theft of Library Materials as Correlates of User Frustration in Public Libraries in Jigawa State

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Abstract

Purpose: This study examined the relationship between physical damage and theft of library materials, and user frustration in public libraries in Jigawa State, Nigeria.

Methodology: The study employed a correlational survey research design. It was guided by two research questions and tested two hypotheses. The population included 1,560 registered users from three public libraries: Dutse Central (602 users), Hadejia (512 users), and Birnin Kudu (446 users). A sample of 455 users was chosen through proportionate stratified random sampling. Data collection involved two validated instruments: the Vandalism of Library Materials Questionnaire (VLMQ) and the User Frustration Questionnaire (UFQ), with reliability confirmed via Cronbach's Alpha (average 0.86 for VLMQ clusters and 0.86 for UFQ). Data analysis was conducted using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Findings: Results showed a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.72$, $p < 0.05$) between physical damage and user frustration, caused by resource scarcity and inadequate user education. A moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.58$, $p < 0.05$) was observed between theft and user frustration, linked to restrictive borrowing policies and socioeconomic factors.

Conclusion: The findings underscore the need for enhanced resource availability, user-centred services, and affordable photocopying services to mitigate vandalism and improve the user experience in Jigawa State's public libraries.

Study type: Research paper.

Keywords: Physical Damage, Theft, Library Materials, User Frustration, Public Libraries, Vandalism.

Introduction

A library is a repository of knowledge, serving as a collection point for the insights of significant thinkers from the past, present, and future. It is often described as a social institution created to gather, organize, conserve, and disseminate informational resources to its users (Anaehobi & Agim, 2019). Traditionally, libraries are categorised into five main types: school, academic, national, public, and special libraries. This study concentrates specifically on public libraries, which are institutions established to provide free access to information, education, and cultural development for all community members. Ibrahim (2019) emphasised that public libraries uphold the principle of the right to access and use information for acquiring knowledge. Their primary aim is to bridge the knowledge divide by ensuring information resources are accessible to everyone, regardless of socio-economic background. The fundamental functions of public libraries include fostering literacy, supporting lifelong learning, promoting community engagement, and serving as cultural and informational hubs (Aina, 2019). They are essential

in providing educational support and fostering a reading culture through diverse resources, including electronic materials, journals, magazines, leaflets, and other library collections. Library materials are valuable information resources that are acquired, processed, and made available to users within the library for learning, recreation, and research purposes. These materials include both printed and electronic formats and are regularly obtained to support the learning and research activities of the academic community. A library without up-to-date materials is ineffective. Although library resources are purchased at a significant expense, vandalism by some users presents challenges, as they damage these materials.

Vandalism of library materials can take many forms, such as damaging, stealing, mutilating, or tearing pages, graffiti, cutting out pages, marking or writing on materials, stealing resources, or hiding these valuable items to benefit one's own selfish interests (Bhat, 2021). Vandalism is defined by Bhat (2021) as the willful or malicious destruction or defacement of any public or private property without the owner's or the controlling person's consent. It is considered an intentional act of loss. Librarians view vandalism of library materials and resources as a threat to intellectual property and regard it as a significant challenge for the library profession worldwide. Handwriting or marks on materials, tearing, or removing pages from books can all be forms of vandalism or mutilation (Bhat, 2021). The hiding of books within libraries is sometimes regarded as a form of material vandalism. Theft and malicious damage to books and other library collections are challenging to address because the chances of being caught are low. At the same time, the likelihood of success is high due to inadequate security measures in libraries. Therefore, vandalism of library materials involves intentionally damaging, defacing, or destroying books, documents, electronic resources, or other library items. This includes both physical damage and theft.

Physical damage to library materials by users is a common challenge faced by public libraries in Nigeria, often leading to frustration among patrons. This issue is pervasive due to a lack of awareness and understanding of how to properly handle library resources. According to Oduwole (2018), the ongoing mishandling of library materials by users —such as tearing pages, marking in books, cracked cases and/or CDs, broken equipment, and mishandling fragile items — reduces the lifespan of resources and can result in costly replacements for the library. User behaviour plays a significant role in the physical damage of library materials. Some users may not know the correct way to handle items, while others may intentionally mistreat them out of negligence or frustration (Adedokun, 2015). Furthermore, overcrowding in the library can hinder staff from effectively monitoring and intervening when users mishandle materials.

Theft of library materials can be defined as the unauthorised taking of library items with the intent to permanently deprive others of their use or access to these materials. The term theft refers to crimes involving the unauthorised taking of a person's property without their permission or consent. Fasae and Adedokun (2019) opined that theft of library material is when information material of any form is taken out of the library in an unauthorised manner by library users. The main reasons for theft in libraries include the high cost of books, insufficient copies in the library, the attractive appearance of books, a lack of user orientation, high demand for certain books, and the absence of photocopying machines, among others. Theft of library materials in public libraries in Nigeria is a common issue that presents significant challenges to their effective operation. The theft not only causes financial losses but also restricts access to valuable resources for other users. The lack of adequate security measures in many public libraries in Nigeria worsens this problem.

Physical damage or theft of library materials is a global issue that has significantly hindered the growth and effectiveness of libraries worldwide. Such acts often lead to user frustration, especially when essential books and information resources are unavailable when needed. Frustration can be defined as an irritable distress resulting from restriction, exclusion, or failure. Aryee and Tetteh (2024) investigated the causes and dynamics of user frustration in academic libraries, identifying poor library policies and operational inefficiencies as contributing factors. In this study, frustration is conceptualised as “(1) the non-fulfilment of an expected gratification, and (2) the instigation to aggression produced by frustration as an inclination towards hostile (or angry), rather than instrumental, aggression” (Aryee & Tetteh, 2024). User frustration in libraries refers to negative emotional reactions that occur when users’ needs and expectations are not met. This frustration may arise from issues such as missing materials, inadequate services, disorganised collections, unhelpful staff, or damage and displacement of books (Nwosu & Eze, 2021). Users might feel anger, annoyance, or disappointment if they cannot access required resources, especially when vandalism has made those resources unusable. As a result, this emotional response can diminish the user’s library experience and hinder their academic or informational pursuits. In public libraries across Nigeria, vandalism of library materials is a serious concern with direct effects on user frustration and satisfaction. However, these issues have not been empirically verified in public libraries in Jigawa State. It is within this context that this study aims to examine physical damage and theft of library materials as factors associated with user frustration in public libraries in Jigawa State.

Statement of the Problem

Public libraries in Jigawa State serve as critical hubs for knowledge dissemination and community engagement, yet users frequently encounter significant frustration when accessing these libraries. This frustration stems from challenges such as limited availability of resources, outdated or insufficient materials, and difficulties in navigating library systems. As a result, misunderstandings and conflicts often arise between library users and staff, creating a strained environment that undermines the purpose of these libraries. The consequences of this frustration are far-reaching, including reduced library patronage, diminished trust in public library services, and a potential decline in educational and intellectual development within the community. Given these issues, it is pertinent to explore whether physical damage to library materials or theft could be significant contributors to the observed user frustration and the resultant conflicts in public libraries in Jigawa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between the physical damage of library materials and user frustration in public libraries in Jigawa State?
2. What is the relationship between theft of library materials and user frustration in public libraries in Jigawa State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance:

There is no significant relationship between the physical damage of library materials and user frustration in public libraries in Jigawa State.

There is no significant relationship between theft of library materials and user frustration in public libraries in Jigawa State.

Literature Review

Physical Damage of Library Materials and User Frustration in Public Libraries

Physical damage, often synonymous with mutilation, refers to the destruction or removal of essential parts of library materials, making them unusable (Tondo et al., 2023). This includes actions such as bending page corners, marking pages with pencil or pen, opening books back-to-back, or tearing out relevant pages (Okafor et al., 2023). Mutilation involves defacement, such as removing pages, articles, illustrations, or entire text blocks from monographs, often with the intention of stealing specific content (Tondo et al., 2023). Such acts are driven by factors such as financial constraints, selfish behaviour, and a scarcity of library materials (Ratcliffe, 2019). Omoike and Alabi (2020) reported a high incidence of book and periodical mutilation in academic libraries, noting practices like underlining, highlighting, and tampering with editorial content. Similarly, Okafor et al. (2023) identified misuse of collections—such as bending book spines, using wet fingers to turn pages, or damaging book spines—as common in university libraries. Ratcliffe (2019) argues that necessity, rather than criminal intent, often drives such behaviour, citing students' dissatisfaction with library services, lack of awareness of replacement costs, and disregard for other users' needs. To address this, Odikpo and Anelobi (2021) recommended providing more photocopiers, affordable photocopying services, and public awareness campaigns to highlight the consequences of mutilation, alongside teaching library ethics to promote a culture of resource protection.

Theft of Library Materials and User Frustration in Public Libraries

Theft of library materials refers to the intentional or unauthorised removal of items without proper checkout procedures (Omoike & Alabi, 2020). This includes taking items out of the library or failing to return them, thereby denying access to others (Nzewi, 2023). Omoike and Alabi (2020) describe theft as the removal of materials by users or staff without adhering to standard procedures. Causes include the high cost of books, insufficient copies, lack of user orientation, and absence of photocopying facilities (Nzewi, 2023). Theft poses a significant global challenge to libraries, affecting both print and non-print materials, particularly high-demand items such as rare books and manuscripts (Adekunle & Adekunjo, 2018). Ukpabi et al. (2021) emphasise the threat to intellectual property, while Aryee and Tetteh (2024) observe that libraries often lag in safeguarding electronic resources from theft and misuse. Similarly, Uzuegbé and Okoro (2021) identify dissatisfaction with library services and lack of awareness of replacement costs as key factors. Emojorho (2021) reported that material loss in the Delta State University Library disrupted services and deprived users of access, which was exacerbated by high material costs.

Methodology

This study utilised a correlational survey research design. The design was selected for its ability to evaluate the direction and strength of relationships between variables. The research was conducted in Jigawa State, located in northwestern Nigeria, covering an area of 23,154 square kilometres with a population of over 5 million (2006 census). The state, mainly agricultural, faces challenges such as poverty and high illiteracy rates, making public libraries vital for delivering educational and agricultural resources. The study focused on three public libraries: Dutse Central Library (with 602 registered users), Hadejia Public Library (with 512 users), and Birnin Kudu Public Library (with 446 users), totalling 1,560 registered users (Jigawa State Public Library records, 2024). By employing proportionate stratified random sampling, a sample of 455 users was chosen—176 from Dutse, 149 from Hadejia, and 130 from Birnin Kudu.

Data were collected using two researcher-developed instruments: the Physical Damage and Theft of Library Materials Questionnaire (PDTLMQ) and the User Frustration Questionnaire (UFQ). The PDTLMQ consists of 20 items, divided into two clusters. Cluster 1 contains 10 items on physical damage of library materials, while Cluster 2 contains 10 items on theft of library materials. The UFQ has 10 items on user frustration. Both instruments were structured on a 4-point scale of strongly agree (4), agree (3), disagree (2), and strongly disagree (1). The instruments were validated by three experts from Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, who ensured alignment with the study's objectives, clarity, and appropriateness. Adjustments were made to align the objectives with the research topic better. Reliability was established using Cronbach's Alpha, yielding coefficients of 0.89 and 0.79 for PDTLMQ clusters (average 0.84) and 0.86 for UFQ, indicating high reliability (Appendix H, p. 117). The researcher, assisted by three library staff members, distributed 450 copies of the instruments across the three libraries over a period of three weeks. Data were analysed using the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient to determine the strength of relationships, interpreted as follows: 0.00–0.20 (very low), 0.20–0.40 (low), 0.40–0.60 (moderate), 0.60–0.80 (high), and 0.80–1.00 (very high). Hypotheses were tested using p-values, with a significance level of 0.05. Null hypotheses were rejected if $p < 0.05$ and retained if $p > 0.05$.

Results

Research Question One: What is the relationship between physical damage to library materials and user frustration in public libraries in Jigawa State?

Table 1: Pearson r on the relationship between physical damage of library materials and user frustration in public libraries in Jigawa State

Source of Variation	N	R	Remark
Physical Damage of Library Material User Frustration	292	0.72	High Positive Relationship

Table 1 illustrates a strong positive correlation between physical damage to library materials and user frustration in public libraries in Jigawa State. This is evidenced by the size of Pearson's Correlation Coefficient r , which is 0.72.

Research Question Two: What is the relationship between theft of library materials and user frustration in public libraries in Jigawa State?

Table 2: Pearson r on the relationship between theft of library materials and user frustration in public libraries in Jigawa State

Source of Variation	N	R	Remark
Theft of Library Materials User Frustration	292	0.58	Moderate Positive Relationship

Table 2 shows that Pearson's $r=0.58$, indicating a moderate positive relationship between theft of library materials and user frustration in public libraries in Jigawa State.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between physical damage of library materials and user frustration in public libraries in Jigawa State.

Table 3: Test of significance of Pearson's correlation between physical damage of library materials and user frustration in public libraries in Jigawa State

Source of Variation	N	R	p-value	Remark
Physical Damage of Library Materials	292	0.72	0.00	Sig

User Frustration

Analysis in Table 3 reveals a significant relationship between physical damage to library materials and user frustration in public libraries in Jigawa State. The calculated r (0.72) has a P -value <0.05 . The first null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between theft of library materials and user frustration in public libraries in Jigawa State.

Table 4: Test of significance of Pearson's correlation between theft of library materials and user frustration in public libraries in Jigawa State.

Source of Variation	N	R	p-value	Remark
Theft of Library Materials	292	0.58	0.00	Sig
User Frustration				

Analysis in Table 6 indicates a significant relationship between theft of library materials and user frustration in public libraries in Jigawa State. The calculated r (0.58) had a P -value <0.05 . The second null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The study revealed a strong positive relationship between physical damage of library materials and user frustration in public libraries in Jigawa State. This is indicated by Pearson's Correlation Coefficient r , which is 0.72. There is a significant relationship between these variables in Jigawa State's libraries, with the calculated r (0.72) having a P -value <0.05 . The results align with Tondo et al. (2023), who reported that theft and mutilation of library resources—including tearing pages, folding pages, and unauthorised borrowing—are common. They further noted that such theft and mutilation lead to issues such as frustration in accessing information, unavailability of resources, and wastage of money and energy. Therefore, the findings are relevant and meaningful, providing evidence of a relationship between physical damage to library materials and user frustration. This may be partly due to the limited availability of resources.

The result revealed that Pearson's $r = 0.58$, indicating a moderate positive relationship between the theft of library materials and user frustration in public libraries in Jigawa State. A significant relationship exists between these two variables in the public libraries of Jigawa State. The calculated r (0.58) had a P -value <0.05 . The result aligns with Nweke's (2019) findings that the extent of theft and mutilation of library resources in academic libraries in Nigeria is very high. The study also revealed that the theft and mutilation of information resources have numerous negative impacts on the entire collection and services of Nigerian academic libraries. Therefore, the finding is relevant and meaningful, as it provides evidence of a relationship between theft of library materials and user frustration. This could be due to increased borrowing restrictions and/or cultural factors.

Conclusion

Based on the study's findings, the researcher concludes that there is a significant relationship between physical damage to library materials and theft, and user frustration in public libraries in Jigawa State, Nigeria. The strong positive correlation between physical damage and user frustration suggests that mutilation, caused by resource scarcity and inadequate user education, greatly restricts access to library materials, thereby increasing user dissatisfaction. Likewise, the moderate positive correlation between theft and user frustration indicates that factors such as restrictive borrowing policies and socioeconomic challenges contribute to the unauthorised removal of materials, further disrupting library services. These findings

emphasise the urgent need for public libraries in Jigawa State to adopt strategies such as increasing resource availability, improving user orientation programmes, and offering affordable photocopying services to reduce physical damage and theft. By addressing these issues, libraries can diminish user frustration, create a more welcoming environment for accessing knowledge, and strengthen their role in supporting educational and community development in Jigawa State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

Maintenance and inventory checks: library management should establish a routine schedule for damage inspections. Regular audits can help identify issues early and reduce user frustration.

Staff training should include theft prevention strategies and customer service skills to address users' concerns effectively. Additionally, the government should implement surveillance systems—such as CCTV cameras and monitoring tools—in libraries to deter potential thieves and boost user confidence.

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